

General Theory of Rhythm

Compositional Examples
Applying Microtime Theory in Practice

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These two compositions were published at *general-theory-of-rhythm.org* in June–July 2015 as concrete examples of the General Theory of Rhythm applied to musical composition and improvisation. Each piece demonstrates specific microtime concepts: phrased tuplets, metric transfiguration, and the harmonic function of rhythmic patterns.

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Crimson Waves

30 juin 2015 by Malcolm Braff — [Leave a Comment](#)

One of my first compositions consciously and intentionally incorporating a multi-functional harmonic microtime system.

I feel it in 7/8 with 11-tuplets except for the bridge and solo part that follows where we clearly switch to an 11/8 with 7-tuplets.

Good Morning Sin City

1 juillet 2015 by Malcolm Braff — [Leave a Comment](#)

Good Morning Sin City is an improvised piece featuring different phrasings used to morph between successive meters.

The musical score for "Good Morning Sin City" consists of five systems of music, each featuring a morphing phrase between two different time signatures. The phrases are marked with "duration ad lib." and percentage indicators (0% and 100%) to show the progression of the morph.

- System 1:** Morphs from 7/8 to 11/8. The phrase starts in 7/8 and gradually transitions to 11/8.
- System 2:** Morphs from 11/8 to 4/4. The phrase starts in 11/8 and gradually transitions to 4/4.
- System 3:** Morphs from 13/8 to 9/8. The phrase starts in 13/8 and gradually transitions to 9/8.
- System 4:** Morphs from 15/8 to 8/8. The phrase starts in 15/8 and gradually transitions to 8/8.
- System 5:** Morphs from 5/4 to 7/8. The phrase starts in 5/4 and gradually transitions to 7/8. The system concludes with the instruction "D.C." (Da Capo).